

Adoption and diffusion of the *protected area downgrading, downsizing, and degazettement (PADDD)* concept in the scientific literature

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Overview

Protected area downgrading, downsizing, and degazettement (PADDD) is a longstanding global phenomenon in which geographic or legal protections are reduced or eliminated for protected areas (PAs). Studies to-date have identified 4,962 enacted and proposed PADDD events across 77 countries, occurring between 1892 and 2021 (Albrecht et al. 2020, Golden Kroner et al. 2019). In the last two decades, the number of observed PADDD events has more than quadrupled, and at a growing rate: 4,100 events have occurred since 2000, and 3,136 events have occurred since 2010.

Within the literature, the concept and term “protected area downgrading, downsizing, and degazettement” and the acronym “PADDD” was first introduced in Mascia and Pailler (2011), published in *Conservation Letters*. Since then, there has been considerable peer-reviewed research identifying other PADDD events as well as their proximate causes, risks, and impacts. To guide future research towards addressing harmful PADDD events worldwide (IUCN 2020), we analyzed the temporal adoption and diffusion of the PADDD concept in the published scientific literature. This analysis demonstrates that PADDD is becoming increasingly well-studied, as PADDD events themselves proliferate. Additional capacity for studying, preventing, and responding to PADDD events in policy and practice continues to be critical to safeguarding the world’s protected areas (Qin et al. 2019).

Methods

We ran two queries in Web of Science: (1) “protected area downgrading, downsizing, and degazettement” and (2) “PADDD”, to obtain a conservative count and distribution of the use of PADDD by author, journal, year, etc. We did not query any individual words of the term (i.e. downgrade, downsize, degazettement) as this yielded extraneous results. We ran the analysis in December 2021 and focused on peer-reviewed publications published between 2011 and 2021.

Caveats:

- This analysis may omit citations that are not indexed in Web of Science, so citation counts may differ from other systems (i.e. Google Scholar).

- There are additional publications that present case studies or analyses of PADDD that do not mention the term explicitly; some of these are included in the PADDD annotated bibliography (Albrecht and Golden Kroner 2021).

Results

Since the publication of Mascia and Pailler (2011), PADDD-related research has grown considerably (Figure 1). Thirty-three published papers mentioned or cited “protected area downgrading, downsizing, and degazettement,” and 78 papers mentioned or cited “PADDD.” Twenty-nine papers appeared in both lists, four papers only used the full term, and 49 papers only used the acronym. Including Mascia and Pailler (2011), PADDD has been mentioned or cited in 82 distinct papers.

Figure 1: Number of publications and citations mentioning “PADDD” over time (from Web of Science), 2011-2021.

The number of times papers that used PADDD were cited has increased every year, from six in 2011 to 585 in 2021 for a total of 2,346, including 8 already slated for upcoming papers in 2022 (statistics from 2022 not pictured in Figure 1). On average, the number of citations per paper has been 28.6 with a median of 7. Only four papers have had more than 100 citations apiece; combined, these have accounted for 1,394, or almost 60% of all citations. The most cited journal was *Nature*, with 861 citations per one paper.

PADDD research has appeared in diverse journals (Table 1). Twenty-two journals have published one or more articles that mentioned or cited “protected area downgrading, downsizing, and degazettement,” and 50 journals have published one or more articles that mentioned or cited “PADDD.” Eighteen journals have published papers that use the full term and acronym; four journals have published papers that only use the full term; and 38 journals

have published papers that only use the acronym. Overall, PADD research that explicitly mentions either the acronym or full term has been published in 54 journals. *Biological Conservation* has published 9 PADD-related papers, roughly 11%, followed by *Conservation Biology* with five and *Environmental Conservation* with four.

Table 1: Citations of publications that included the term “PADD” by journal

Journal	Papers	Citations	Citations per Paper	Citations (% of total)
<i>Nature</i>	1	861	861	36.7
<i>Conservation Letters</i>	4	289	72.3	12.3
<i>Conservation Biology</i>	5	268	53.6	11.4
<i>Biological Conservation</i>	9	265	29.4	11.3
<i>Science</i>	2	98	49	4.2
<i>Global Change Biology</i>	1	49	49	2.1
<i>Anthropocene</i>	1	47	47	2
<i>Oryx</i>	2	43	21.5	1.8
<i>Ecological Indicators</i>	3	40	13.3	1.7
<i>PNAS</i>	1	36	36	1.5
Others	53	350	0–29	14.9
Total	82	2,346	--	100

We identified the top ten journals that published papers mentioning “PADD” (Figure 2). Most journals are focused on ecology and conservation-related topics.

Figure 2: Top 10 journals by frequency mentioning “PADD” (from Web of Science).

We also identified the top authors involved in publishing peer-reviewed papers on PADDD and their institutions (Figure 3, 4). Home institutions of these authors are located in the United States, Brazil, Australia, the United Kingdom, and Germany.

Figure 3: Top 10 authors by frequency on publications mentioning "PADDD" (from Web of Science).

Figure 4: Top 10 author institutions by frequency from publications mentioning "PADDD" (from Web of Science).

Attachment: PADDD Citation Report (.xls), with full list of citation statistics

Citations

Albrecht, R., & Golden Kroner, R.E. (2020). PADDD Annotated Bibliography, Version 1.1 (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3973671>

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